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Neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy of rectal cancer: Is VMAT/SIB techniques superior to 3D conformal radiotherapy?

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Introduction: Neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy is a standard treatment modality for locally advanced rectal cancer. Modern radiation-delivering techniques such as Volumetric Modulated Arc Therapy with simultaneous integrated boost (VMAT/SIB) allow for a dose escalation to the target volume. The aim of this study is to compare the clinical response following neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy of patients with rectal cancer using VMAT SIB and 3D conformal radiation technique.

Materials and methods: Patients treated for primary rectal adenocarcinoma of stage T1-T4, N0-N2, M0, using neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy between the years 2018. and 2020. were included in the study, retrospectively. Both VMAT/SIB and 3D conformal techniques were used. Clinical response was assessed based on a pelvic MRI after chemoradiation. The Chi square test and the Mann-Whitney test were used to analyze the collected data.

Results: Total of 61 patients have fulfilled inclusion criteria. Thirty patients were treated with VMAT/SIB technique, receiving 46Gy and 57,5 Gy in 23 fractions, 31 were treated using 3D conformal technique receiving 45Gy in 25 fractions with boost of 5,4Gy in 3 fractions. All of the patients underwent MRI 6-8 weeks after chemoiradiation. Complete clinical response was achieved in 9 (30%) patients in the VMAT/SIB group and in 1 (3,22%) patient in the 3D conformal group ($p = 0,005$).

Conclusion: This study has shown that VMAT/SIB is superior to 3D conformal radiation technique in achieving complete clinical response after chemoidadiation of rectal cancer.

Keywords: VMAT/SIB, 3D conformal, neoadjuvant chemoradiation, rectal cancer

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